

Rostering practices and ATCO productivity in Area Control Centres

How much spare capacity is there and how to make best use of it?

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Abstract — The process of staff planning and rostering in ANSPs has a considerable effect on ATCO productivity and, consequently, on capacity and cost-efficiency delivered to airspace users. The aim of this paper is twofold. Firstly, to establish a relationship between ACC taskload (represented by daily capacity profiles), rostering flexibility in place and the number of ATCOs needed. And secondly - to explore how varying rostering practices applied in ACCs affect spare capacity in the system. To that end, an initial mathematical model for optimizing ATCO staffing requirements has been proposed and tested on a case study involving three ACCs, reflecting different hourly variability in demand. The results suggest that - for different combinations of shift patterns and capacity profiles - substantial variation exists in both the minimum number of ATCOs (needed) and the associated spare ACC capacity. It has also been shown that a certain amount of spare capacity is inevitably present in the system due to inability to perfectly match ATCO hours with demand. Different options and enablers for exploiting such capacity are also discussed in the paper.

Keywords - air traffic control; ATCO; rostering; area control centre; capacity; productivity; virtualisation; ATM performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to its comparative advantages over other transport modes, air transport plays an important role in ensuring the mobility of people and goods around the globe and thus represents a strong catalyst for economic development. Despite the current global crisis caused by COVID-19 pandemic and associated traffic downturn, strong recovery and further increase in demand is expected in years and decades to come, requiring significant investments in physical infrastructure, as well as organizational changes in the Air Traffic Management (ATM) system in order to ensure further sustainable growth.

Matching demand and supply represents an important challenge for many complex systems, including ATM. The efficiency of such process greatly determines the resulting performance and service quality delivered to the airspace users and society in general. In Europe, the greatest attention is devoted to achieving optimum ATM performance in four key areas: safety, capacity, cost-efficiency and environment [1]. At the same time, one of the key detrimental factors contributing to suboptimal network performance in Europe remains high ATM fragmentation [2]. Namely, the provision of Air Navigation Services (ANS) is mainly organized at national level through Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs) who independently plan and exploit their human and infrastructure resources in order to provide an adequate level of service to airspace users.

In the proposal for the future architecture of the European airspace [3], it was recognized that extreme delays in Europe over the past few years were mainly caused by strategic recruitment choices, unexpected shifts in demand and sub-optimal deployment of staff in some Area Control Centres (ACCs) in Europe, leading to opening fewer sectors than initially foreseen. And indeed, delays attributed to Air Traffic Control (ATC) capacity and staffing reasons represented more than 60% of the total ATFM delays in Europe during 2019 [4].

Staff planning in ANSPs is a long and iterative process. It starts from identification of the future staffing needs based on traffic forecast in order to select, recruit and train Air Traffic Control Officers (ATCOs). The process continues with shift/roster design and personnel allocation based on updated demand information. Given the fact that capacity adjustments at short notice in ANSPs are fairly limited due to long lead time needed for training and hardly any inter-ANSP ATCO mobility, an efficient utilization of

¹ The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not represent a policy or position of EUROCONTROL.

existing resources is of paramount importance. As duly recognized in several recent publications [3, 5, 6], flexibility in ATCO rostering plays a crucial role in adapting capacity to traffic demand, while ATCO shifts represent one of the key drivers of ATCO employment cost in ACCs [7].

The aim of this paper is twofold. Firstly, to establish a relationship between ACC taskload, rostering flexibility in place and the number of ATCOs needed. And secondly - to explore how varying rostering practices applied in ACCs affect spare capacity in the system. The results of the initial numerical experiments conducted are then discussed in order to better understand the main determinants of ATCO productivity in ACCs, as well as to identify the conditions under which potential spare capacity could be further unlocked.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II outlines the key aspects of capacity management and ATCO rostering in ANSPs and gives an overview of previous research. Section III describes the mathematical model used to estimate the ATCO staffing requirements, while Section IV presents the case study and summarizes the results of numerical experiments. Conclusion and ideas for further work are outlined in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND AND PREVIOUS RESEARCH

A. Capacity management – general remarks

Capacity management in ANSPs represents an iterative rolling process with the main goal of providing sufficient capacity in order to accommodate traffic demand without imposing significant operational, economic or environmental penalties under normal circumstances [8]. It starts with airspace design and defining overall staffing needs based on traffic forecast in the long-term planning phase. Subsequent refinements and a more detailed capacity planning and allocation of resources at strategic and pre-tactical levels are needed in order to deliver a certain (required and/or acceptable) level of service on the day of operations itself (tactical phase).

In general, the amount of capacity required at any given time is proportional to traffic demand, while it is also affected by traffic complexity and other factors internal to the ANSP (e.g. technological advancement, ATCO experience etc.). While the overall requirement is to ensure sustainable capacity/staffing levels over longer periods of time (taking into account vacations, training, sickness leaves etc.), it can be said that staffing needs on a single day of operations are determined by the number of sectors open at any point in time (hereinafter referred to as “Daily Capacity Profile – DCP”).

Namely, in order to accommodate traffic demand, airspace is divided into segments, called elementary sectors, which can be

combined to form collapsed sectors. Within each sector, ATCOs usually work in pairs, where one controller (planner) is responsible for planning and coordination of flights entering and leaving a sector, while the second (executive) controller tactically manages traffic and ensures necessary separation between flights. Due to workload and safety considerations, there is a limit in the number of flights served by a single pair of ATCOs during a certain period of time. Depending on traffic and its distribution in the area of responsibility of a given ACC, at each point in time a certain group of sectors is active and forms a sector configuration. Sector Opening Scheme (SOS) specifies sector configurations in use at any time during a single day of operations, effectively defining the shape of the DCP.

Therefore, with the usual increase in traffic demand during a day, more sectors are opened and staffed by ATCOs in order to provide an acceptable level of service and avoid delays. Analogously, during periods of lower traffic (e.g. night), airspace is again combined in larger segments and fewer ATCOs are needed to cover active sector configurations.

B. ATCO rostering problem and previous research

Due to their nature and constraints involved, personnel scheduling problems are in general considered to be among the most complex combinatorial optimization problems and as such have been heavily investigated over the past few decades. One of the most frequently studied examples is the nurse rostering problem [9,10]. However, personnel scheduling is an important challenge for many other industries, including ATM.

De Causmaecker et al. [11] examined some real-world personnel scheduling problems in order to come up with their common classification. Four categories of such problems have been identified, while the associated models and complexity are further discussed in [12]. Due to variable nature of air traffic demand and associated uncertainty, planning and scheduling of ATCOs can be considered as “fluctuation-centred” planning problem, where the allocation of workforce and tasks depends on a continuously changing demand [11].

An extensive overview, methodology and guidelines for ATCO manpower planning process have been outlined as part of two relevant ATM programmes in late 1990s: European Air Traffic Control Harmonisation and Integration Programme (EATCHIP) [13] and European Air Traffic Management (ATM) Programme (EATMP) [14]. This was subsequently supported by a comprehensive study on shiftwork practices in ATM and related industries [15]. Several other relevant publications focus on human performance in ATM [16], fatigue management [17, 18] and impact of age, experience and automation [19].

In general, it can be said that ATCO rostering is influenced by two main groups of factors:

- *External factors* (traffic demand characteristics, regulatory framework etc.);
- *Internal factors* (operational environment, rostering practices, labour agreements etc.).

When it comes to modelling, these factors result in model constraints which can be *hard* (conditions that are required to be satisfied by any feasible solution - e.g. regulatory requirements) and *soft* (usually reflecting ATCO preferences). Some of the typical hard constraints involved in ATCO scheduling problem are those related to roster cycles, number of different shifts, their start and end times, minimum and maximum shift lengths, minimum rest time between consecutive shifts, maximum consecutive time at the Controller Working Position (CWP), minimum break away from the position etc.

Only a handful of research contributions addressing ATCO scheduling have been published in the past decade, most of which were focused on local problems and/or testing different solving approaches. There have been hardly any attempts to examine the relationship between demand profile, sector openings, staffing needs and associated spare capacity at ACCs in a more systematic way, which is considered to be the main contribution of this paper.

In [20], a formal definition of Air Traffic Controller Shift Scheduling Problem (ATCoSSP) was given. The author tested different exact methods to generate staff schedules for a tower/terminal ATC unit. Conniss et al. [21] have developed a greedy heuristic algorithm to produce feasible daily rosters with the goal of maintaining ATCO currency in different operational positions. Josefsson et al. [22] presented an optimization framework for efficient ATCO shift scheduling at the remote tower centre (RTC).

Another, more recent group of relevant publications tackles ATCO scheduling problem in an en-route/ACC environment, which is also the main focus of this paper. Tello et al. [23] proposed a three-phase approach to solve ATCO work-shift scheduling problem, where a set of labour conditions have to be satisfied, given the fixed number of ATCOs available and an airspace sector configuration to be covered. The same authors in [24] compared the performance of a methodology based on variable neighbourhood search (VNS) against simulated annealing using a more complex instance of the problem.

III. MATCHING ATCO NUMBERS WITH DEMAND

Despite sharing some common features and constraints, personnel planning and scheduling in ATM is quite specific in its own right. The paramount importance of maintaining highest safety levels, traffic volatility and complexity, specific operational environment and labour relations (requiring stricter set of constraints) are just few of them.

As mentioned before, ATCO planning and rostering involves several phases with different constraints and level of uncertainty, related to both demand materialization and staff availability. In this paper we focus on a single day of operations and the problem of finding the minimum number of ATCOs to cover a given DCP, depending on demand profile and the level of rostering flexibility. This also allows to obtain an estimate of resulting spare capacity and its temporal distribution, which in turn improves the understanding of the notion of ATCO productivity and its key determinants.

Since the goal of this study is to examine the general relationship between traffic demand and staffing needs, some of the constraints that are specific to individual ACCs and their operational environment are not included in the model (e.g. different sector families, ATCO licenses and qualifications etc.). Also, the paper focuses solely on ATCOs and does not take into account supervisors, flow managers and other operational staff that may be involved in the operation of an ACC, as their numbers typically do not depend on traffic levels, but rather on local organizational and procedural specificities.

A. *Mathematical model*

Several modelling approaches have been examined and tested in order to come up with a model that is suitable and sufficiently realistic for the main purpose of this study. In general, there are two common approaches to modelling ATCO rostering problems. The first one is to explicitly set all constraints, in which case the model determines whether an ATCO should be at the operational position or not in each time period within the timeframe considered. However, this approach is computationally very expensive. In order to reduce the search space, it is possible to reduce some of the constraints by introducing pre-defined working templates for ATCOs, resembling the usual sequence of alternating work/break periods during a typical shift (e.g. 2 hours on/30 min off). Such approach significantly reduces the computational complexity of the problem and all instances are typically solved within a few seconds. Therefore, in this paper only a model with pre-defined templates will be presented.

The notation used is summarized as follows:

Sets:

A	Set of ATCO pairs (1 pair = 2 ATCOs: planner + executive)
T	Set of time periods during a day
$M \subset T$	Set of time periods when shifts are allowed to start
$P = \{1, \dots, ts\}$	Set of time periods during one shift, where ts is the number of time periods during one shift
S	Set of pre-defined working templates

Parameters:

ns_t	The number of active sectors in time period t
$wb_{s,t}$	An (0,1) indicator denoting if an ATCO pair works at the CWP or takes a break in template $s \in S$ at time period $t \in P$

Variables:

$$z_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if ATCO pair } i \in A \text{ is assigned to any shift;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$x_{ist} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if ATCO pair } i \in A \text{ works according to template } \\ & s \in S \text{ in a shift that starts from time period } t \in M; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The problem is formulated as the Linear Integer Program (LIP) with the following objective and constraints:

$$(\min) \quad f(x) = \sum_{i \in A} z_i \quad (1)$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{t \in M} x_{ist} \leq z_i \quad i \in A \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i \in A} \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{\substack{k \in M: \\ \max\{1, t-ts+1\} \leq k \leq t}} wb_s(t-k+1)x_{isk} \geq ns_t \quad t \in T \quad (3)$$

$$x_{ist} \in \{0,1\} \quad \begin{matrix} i \in A, \\ s \in S, \\ t \in T \end{matrix} \quad (4)$$

$$z_i \in \{0,1\} \quad i \in A \quad (5)$$

The objective (1) is to minimize the number of ATCO pairs engaged during one day of operations, represented by a given DCP. Constraint (2) ensures the link between variables x_{ist} and z_i , i.e. an ATCO pair is considered engaged ($z_i = 1$) only if it is assigned to a shift. The same constraint also ensures that the number of shifts assigned to an ATCO pair does not exceed 1. Constraint (3) secures that the minimum number of available ATCO pairs at any time period is greater than the number of open sectors in the same period, while constraints (4) and (5) define limitations for decision variables.

IV. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

A. Case study

Traffic characteristics and local operational environment have a significant effect on the rostering system applied at a specific ATC unit. While the organization of service provision in tower/terminal environment has its own specificities, in this paper we focus on en-route environment, managed by ACCs.

As described in Section II, with the increase in traffic during the day, different sector configurations consisting of a specific set of sectors are being used. This results in the DCP that could be used as a proxy of the total daily taskload encountered by a particular ACC and directly affecting the number of ATCOs needed. In general, the shape (see Fig. 1) of the DCP is dependent on the traffic load: everything else equal, the more aircraft are present within the area of responsibility, the more sectors are opened, and vice versa. For example, during night only one or two sectors are usually open, with the span and duration of such a ‘‘calm’’ period varying strongly between ACCs.

The aim of this paper is not to replicate any specific ATC centre and its local operational and/or social conditions, but rather to assess general dependencies between traffic demand, rostering flexibility and the number of ATCOs needed. Consequently, the model presented in previous section was tested with a few typical scenarios occurring in the European ATM network. Representative DCPs planned for the summer period by different ACCs (as outlined in the Network Operations Plan [25]) have been evaluated in order to come up with a few distinctive capacity profiles. Three DCPs with different levels of hourly variability in sector openings have been selected for the case study (see Fig. 1):

- ACC 1 - high variability (peak/average ratio=1.77);
- ACC 2 - medium variability (peak/average = 1.55);
- ACC 3 - low variability (peak/average = 1.2).

In order to obtain staffing requirements for a range of daily capacity levels, sector-hours were gradually added (at uneven intervals) to the base DCP of 24 sector-hours (representing ‘‘minimum-service’’ scenario of one sector open at any time

during a day). At the same time, the overall hourly distribution of the selected DCPs was preserved. Therefore, for each of the three profiles shown in Figure 1, the minimum number of ATCOs was iteratively determined for varying levels of the total sector-hours in order to assess the relationship between staffing requirements and the overall daily ACC taskload.

Figure 1. Planned DCPs of the three ACCs from the Network Operations Plan (NOP) selected for the case study

B. Assumptions and parameters

Regarding model parameters, our aim was to replicate the most common set of rules that is typically observed in European ANSPs². The time scale interval used for all the inputs into the model is 15 minutes (i.e. 96 time periods during 24h). Maximum consecutive time at CWP is limited to 2 hours (8 periods), with a minimum duration of break away from the position of 30 minutes (2 periods). The maximum shift duration is set at 8 hours (32 periods). As already mentioned, these parameters were not explicitly set as constraints, but rather represented an input for defining the ATCO working templates.

Time for briefings before taking up duty, as well as time needed for handovers at the operational position were considered to be relatively short and therefore have not been taken into account (several ACCs in Europe have already deployed e-Briefing tools allowing ATCOs to read their briefing notes before coming to work, while handovers usually take up to 5 minutes).

While there are a number of factors affecting ATCO scheduling (and resulting productivity) at different planning stages, in this paper we consider the number of possible shifts during a day as a proxy of the level of rostering flexibility. In this regard, it should be noted that shifts are only defined as placeholders for the model to determine an optimal ATCO allocation, which means that not all of the pre-defined shifts need to be staffed in the model output.

Four different shift patterns were tested:

- Basic pattern with 3 shifts (starting at 6AM, 2PM and 10PM respectively);
- 6 shifts (3 basic shifts + 3 staggered shifts arranged in increments of 2 hours starting from 8 AM);
- 10 shifts (3 basic shifts + 7 staggered shifts in increments of 1 hour starting from 7AM);
- 18 shifts (3 basic shifts + 15 staggered shifts in increments of 30 minutes starting from 06:30AM).

It should be noted that possible starting times of additional (staggered) shifts are distributed in the first half of the day (until 2PM) when traffic usually picks up, while their duration extends also into the afternoon period (see Figure 2).

² For this purpose, an extensive survey of rostering practices currently applied in ACCs throughout Europe has previously been conducted. Responses from 11 ACCs (covering small, medium and large ANSPs) have been received and analyzed in order to set model parameters.

Figure 2. Distribution of shifts during a day (3 basic shifts are shown in gray, while 3, 7 and 15 additional shifts are colored yellow, orange and red respectively)

C. Results and discussion

While there are a number of different aspects to consider when assessing capacity and productivity at an ACC (e.g. sector load, different sector configurations, ATCO experience etc.), in this paper we focus on two cost-efficiency and productivity indicators:

- Overall staffing requirements (the minimum number of ATCOs needed to cover a given SOS);
- Associated spare capacity (defined as the share of “unused” ATCO hours, assuming the minimum required number of ATCOs on duty and taking into account breaks).

In order to accommodate varying traffic demand, ATCOs are deployed in chunks (shifts) during a day. They have a certain limited duration (usually 8 hours) and are not divisible, i.e. it is normally not possible to call an ATCO on duty twice (in two different shifts) during a single day of operations. This implies that ATCO productivity highly depends on how well capacity available is adjusted to fluctuating traffic demand, which in turn is largely driven by the shift patterns in use at a given ACC.

Figure 3 shows results obtained for the different demand levels (expressed in sector-hours) and profiles (in line with the three selected DCPs). Irrespective of the rostering flexibility in place, the minimum number of ATCOs needed to cover the basic DCP with 24 sector-hours is 12 (6 pairs), i.e. at least 2 ATCO pairs should be available at any point in time due to necessary breaks away from the position. The number of shifts in this case is not relevant and 3 basic shifts covering the whole day of operations are sufficient.

With the rise in sector-hours, variation in ATCO numbers for the different levels of rostering flexibility gradually increases. This can be explained by the fact that higher demand levels are also followed by larger differences in hourly variability, requiring

more shifts in order to better match staffing with demand. In general, the number of ATCOs increases linearly ($R^2 > 0.95$), albeit with varying slopes (lines diverging to the right). As an example, regression coefficients decrease from 0.39 (with 3 shifts) to 0.33 (18 shifts) for the case of ACC1. In the tested range of total sector-hours, the associated reduction in the number of ATCOs reaches up to 20% (or up to 8 ATCOs). Potential cost savings can only be fully considered at earlier (strategic) planning stages and direct monetization is difficult to establish. As an indication, average ATCO employment costs per ATCO-hour at Pan-European system level are estimated at 115€ in 2018[26].

As expected, savings in ATCO numbers due to more flexible shift patterns gradually reduce with the flattening of the demand profile and practically diminish in the case of flattest profile (ACC 3 - green). However, the increase in ATCOs needed with sector-hours is generally slower for the smoother profiles (slope coefficient drops to 0.3).

When it comes to spare capacity (right-hand scale in Fig. 3), it can be observed that the largest capacity wastage occurs in low traffic conditions. This is pretty intuitive, as ATCO hours are added in large(r) chunks and their number in such circumstances (due to minimum staffing requirements) greatly exceeds the number of sector-hours that have to be delivered. Therefore, spare capacity starts from almost 40% in the basic 24 sector-hours case and then gradually decreases depending on the number of shifts and DCP shape. Unsurprisingly, spare capacity is lower when more shifts are available and fewer ATCOs are needed. However, even in the most flexible pattern with 18 shifts there are still unused ATCO hours due to inability to perfectly match supply with demand.

It is important to note that these results were obtained under the assumption of full prior knowledge of the sector openings for a particular day of operations. In reality, this is rarely the case due to traffic uncertainty caused by various factors materializing only closer to the flight execution. For this reason, ANSPs include

capacity buffers at various stages during their planning process [5], so the amount of spare capacity might be even underestimated in this study. Other sources of uncertainty include the overall traffic deviation from forecast, suboptimal capacity planning by individual ANSPs, seasonal/weekly traffic variability, spatio-temporal traffic shifts due to weather, political crises, disruptions, changes in route charges etc.

Figure 3. Number of ATCOs needed (left vertical axis) and associated spare ATCO hours (right vertical axis) as a function of the total sector-hours

While recognizing the fact that certain amount of spare capacity is inevitably present in the system, a very relevant question is how this capacity could potentially be unlocked for the benefit of airspace users. The first and obvious possibility not requiring any specific technological enablers is to increase the level of ATCO rostering flexibility. There are already successful examples of such developments among ANSPs that have proven their contribution to increased productivity (e.g. in MUAC [27]). Nevertheless, the evolution towards increased rostering flexibility is always coupled with social aspect and it is not straightforward to achieve the right balance.

Another prospective set of opportunities arises from the recent developments in virtualization and sector-independent ATCO licensing concepts. Initial plans for decoupling Air Traffic Services (ATS) from ATM data services have already been outlined in relevant studies [3, 28]. This in turn would pave the way for the introduction of “capacity-on-demand” (COD) service, described as “a temporary delegation of the provision of air traffic services to an alternate provider with spare capacity”. The advantages of such a concept are apparent both for ANSP offering spare capacity (increased productivity and potentially extra revenue) and for ANSP requesting additional capacity (improved service quality).

The extent of benefits from COD service would depend on the level of integration and interoperability between cooperating ANSPs. Two very important questions to that end are: 1) when the information on required/spare capacity becomes available to capacity planners; and 2) what is the level of flexibility when deploying it somewhere else in the system. The first question is tightly linked with the level of uncertainty in both demand and available capacity at different planning stages. Intuitively, ANSPs would strive to satisfy their own capacity needs before offering any spare capacity to the network.

When it comes to the level of cross-border cooperation between ANSPs, several implementation scenarios are presently being studied, ranging from baseline and non-tactical to more demanding and time-critical virtual center scenarios [28]. Highly relevant example of such dynamic, time-critical cross-border ANS provision at regional level is the on-going FINEST (Finnish-Estonian Integrated Services of ANSPs) project [29], aiming at dynamically transferable ATS provision between the Tallinn and Helsinki ACCs. Another example is a local virtual center, allowing high integration of ACCs within one ANSP [30].

Results presented in this paper indicate certain synergy opportunities among ANSPs (e.g. with “complementary” demand profiles) that could be further exploited at earlier (strategic and/or pre-tactical) planning stages, thus achieving greater cost-efficiency benefits.

V. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

In this paper we presented an initial model for optimizing ATCO staffing requirements in an ACC for a single day of operations, based on planned/expected capacity profiles. Results of the case study involving three representative ACCs demonstrate substantial role of rostering flexibility in reaching higher productivity and cost-efficiency levels. It has also been shown that spare capacity inevitably arises in the system due to inability to perfectly match capacity with traffic demand. Results can be further extended by analyzing a wider range of demand profiles and/or changing model parameters in order to assess sensitivity to varying rostering practices. Introducing additional constraints related to different operational environments and local procedures would be useful for the potential application of the model in studies focused on particular ANSPs. This also includes adding soft constraints reflecting specific ATCO preferences.

Very relevant and promising way forward is to explore ways of exploiting spare capacity and increasing the level of scalability and resilience of the system [31, 32]. Virtualization and sector-independent ATS operations are expected to become key enablers for more flexible use of resources through cross-border service provision [3]. In that respect, further research could identify potential pairs/groups of ANSPs that are best positioned to benefit from cross-border operations, depending on their local demand characteristics, rostering practices, technological similarity etc.

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